

MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE THROUGH DEVELOPING STUDENTS' PHYSICAL CULTURE

Z. Musayev

Doctoral student at Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15266840>

Abstract. *This article discusses the mechanisms for improving a healthy lifestyle through the development of students' physical culture, the formation of scientific views, approaches, and methods for improving the main areas of physical education, sports, and a healthy lifestyle.*

Keywords: *healthy generation, physical education and sports, healthy lifestyle, movement, physical activity.*

INTRODUCTION

A healthy person is the pillar of the state, the pride of the nation, and its successor. What do we mean by a healthy life and a healthy lifestyle? A healthy lifestyle is a complex dynamic process that is aimed at maintaining one's health and strengthening one's body, preventing diseases, and building resilience to the external environment through physical training. People who follow the rules of a healthy lifestyle are not only physically strong and resilient, but also mentally stable.

It is aimed at systematically promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, further strengthening the principles of a healthy lifestyle in society, protecting the growing younger generation from harmful habits, and forming a system for effectively organizing physical education and sports activities in each neighborhood, educational institutions, labor collectives, etc.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4063 dated December 18, 2018 “On measures to prevent non-communicable diseases, support a healthy lifestyle and increase the level of physical activity of the population”, the Ministry of Physical Education and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations are tasked with organizing the regular holding of the “Alpomish” and “Barchinoy” tests among wide segments of the population, which include sports standards that determine the general physical fitness of the population depending on their age, and encouraging the winners and prize-winners with badges of the III, II, and I degrees.

Since our country gained independence, our society has paid more attention to young people, who are the creators of our future. Positive changes can be seen at every step, especially in the field of youth health.

Today, no matter what type of institution belongs to the public education system, doctors and qualified nurses provide services there.

Extensive work has been carried out to protect the health of secondary school students, provide them with qualified medical care, identify sick students in a timely manner, improve their health, and prevent various diseases.

To conduct physical education sessions, you can use a special set of exercises consisting of 3-4 exercises. In educational institutions, it is necessary to conduct exercises that have a mental and static load on individual students, the system and the whole organism, a physical education

minute to prevent general fatigue in the lesson, and exercises with a general effect, consisting of exercises for different groups of muscles, taking into account the tension during the lesson. The exercises last 1.5-2 minutes. Schools should create conditions to meet students' biological needs for movement. This requirement can be met by more than 2 hours of daily physical activity for children and adolescents.

There are various guidelines and methods for forming and raising a healthy generation. It is especially important to properly organize children's free time and teach them various national movement games.

Today, developing a healthy lifestyle is as important as ever, and this issue is studied as a social problem, just as it was in the past.

The 21st century is a time of high speed, a huge flow of information, and rapidly changing events, so each person must find his own world, his own environment, and his own interests. The 21st century is different from other centuries in terms of the development of technology, informatization, and computerization. However, public opinion and the media shape the consumer attitude to life in the younger generation.

There is a belief that in this life you should try everything, that is, alcohol, tobacco, and drugs. Accordingly, the problem of drug addiction among young people remains relevant, which leads to poor social behavior, deterioration of health, and a decrease in mental and creative potential.

Not all young people engage in physical education and sports, most are exempted for medical reasons. Thus, in modern society there are a number of problems related to the health of the younger generation, in particular, the ability of young people to consciously and purposefully lead a healthy lifestyle. The human body is a unique complex self-regulating biological system that is in constant interaction with the changing conditions of the external environment.

Health is understood in the broadest sense of the word. It is not only the absence of disease, but also a state of complete physical, moral, ethical, psycho-emotional, social, and intellectual well-being.

A healthy lifestyle is the only possible way to maintain and strengthen human health. The necessary components of a healthy lifestyle are:

- physical activity,
- positive emotions,
- alertness,
- personal hygiene,
- daily routine,
- balanced nutrition,
- temperament,
- positive thinking.

Health promotion activities are joint activities of a student-athlete and a teacher-coach, aimed, on the one hand, at improving the individual, and, on the other hand, at changing the value attitude towards one's own health and mastering the attitude towards one's own health.

The problem of maintaining health has always interested humanity.

In our age of stressful overloads and serious environmental degradation, this problem is especially relevant and occupies an important place in the system of social values and priorities of society.

Factors that negatively affect the formation of a healthy lifestyle, harmful habits, and ways to eliminate them have been studied in the works of pedagogical scientists M. Abdulaziz, M. Akhmedov, M. Akhmatov, M. Ikromova, O. Najmiddinov, I. Nasritdinov, Kh. Rakhmatov, T. Uzokov, and others.

Physiologist B. Chumakov developed recommendations for students on playing sports, eating properly, following a daily routine, avoiding harmful consequences, and getting proper rest.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Personal hygiene of students includes many issues related to the daily routine. These include timely washing and cleaning of the body and oral cavity, giving up bad habits that harm health and exercise, and others. A school student's daily routine is expected to include: sleep, meals, studying at school, preparing lessons at home, walking in the fresh air, homework, doing favorite things, participating in various activities outside of class and school, and following personal hygiene rules. The daily routine should include active activities such as morning physical education and fun sports. Therefore, adhering to the daily routine is an important factor in maintaining health and achieving success in class.

We believe that the cooperation between school, family, teachers, students, and parents is an important tool for implementing physical education, which further improves the quality of work, and a healthy lifestyle into the daily lives of students. It is important for a child to engage in physical education and sports in order to develop healthily and comprehensively. We need to explain to students during the lesson the importance of physical education in strengthening human health.

A person who engages in physical education becomes strong, agile, resilient, strong-willed, courageous, beautiful, and mobile. Therefore, he tries to perform each movement independently, well and with minimal effort. According to historical sources, the national sports and national games of the Uzbek people varied depending on the living conditions of the population and prepared people for active, productive work.

Physical illiteracy should be combated at an early age, in kindergartens and preschools. Early education for physical literacy can play an important role and be an integral part of the process of promoting the development of a healthy lifestyle. It would be appropriate to start the basic program of physical literacy in kindergartens for children under 6 years of age in the form of games and interesting exercises.

In the traditional educational process, students spend most of their time sitting. Therefore, teachers need to monitor students' sitting postures during lessons, conduct physical education sessions in lessons, organize a positive sequence of movements, and include exercises aimed at maintaining proper posture in physical education exercises. Performing exercises to music will give an even more positive effect. It is necessary to pay attention to the formation of correct sitting in first-graders from the first day of school. Educators should teach children simple methods of controlling their sitting posture at school and at home. Educators should patiently observe the child's sitting posture in primary grades. In the hunched position necessary for writing, the back muscles are strained, the heart rate increases, and the amplitude of breathing decreases. In this case, to maintain balance, students lean on the table with their chest, which further complicates the work of internal organs. Therefore, the supervision of primary school teachers is of great importance for the health of children. Conducting physical education sessions in lessons is an effective means of maintaining the employability of students.

Movement is life, but active movement is a healthy life. Daily sports activities are a guarantee of beauty and health. In addition to the benefits of sports, it is important that they are fun, and for this you need to choose a sport that suits you. The best sport for women is regular swimming, for those who lead a sedentary lifestyle, walking or hiking is ideal, jogging at the same speed can be done by the whole family, as well as cycling, in winter you should not forget about it. Skiing and skating. It should be remembered that any sport, if approached incorrectly, is traumatic.

The relevance of a healthy lifestyle is associated with the increasing and changing burden on the human body as a result of the complexity of social life and the intensification of technogenic, environmental, psychological, political, and military risks.

A healthy lifestyle is an active participation in work, social, family and household, and leisure forms of human life. Optimal work and sufficient rest also affect our health. Vigorous activity has a beneficial effect not only on the physical, but also on the mental nervous system, strengthens the heart, blood vessels and the whole body. There is a certain law of labor that is known to many. People engaged in physical labor need rest, which is not associated with physical activity, and it is better if mental stress is eliminated during rest.

To protect children's health, foster a healthy lifestyle, and ultimately create a healthy generation, it is essential to provide students with medical and hygienic knowledge.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we will highlight the following key factors in preventing students from contracting diseases and fostering a healthy lifestyle in educational institutions:

- conduct in-depth medical examinations and health improvement measures for students, taking into account environmental and climatic conditions;
- conduct preventive and health improvement measures in a coherent and consistent manner;
- send students in need of health improvement to health improvement institutions;
- ensure that teachers and educators have sufficient medical and hygienic knowledge in forming a healthy lifestyle for primary school students;
- work in collaboration with medical workers and parents in implementing the health improvement program;
- monitor the correct organization of the students' daily routine by parents and teachers.

If we want our society to be both physically and spiritually healthy, and if we want high spirituality, morality, and a healthy mind to be the product of a healthy body, then "Sport for All" must become the main motto of the policy of promoting a healthy lifestyle.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 7-fevraldagi PF-4947-sonli «O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida»gi Farmoni. O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonun hujjatlari to'plami, 2017 yil, 6-son, 70-modda.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi 5111700 – Boshlang'ich ta'lim bakalavriat ta'lim yo'nalishining malaka talablari. Toshkent. 2018.08.25. 40 b. (3 b.)
3. Richard E. Boyatzis. David C. McClelland: For The Wiley Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences Volume IV: Clinical, Applied and Cross – Cultural Research. December 5, 2016

4. J.Raven (1984). Competence in modern society: Its Identification, Development and Release. – UK. P.220
5. Маркова А.К. Психология профессионализма. – М.: Знание, 1996. – 340 с.
6. Musurmonova O. Pedagogik texnologiyalar – ta’lim samaradorligi omili. Monografiya. – T.: Yoshlar nashriyot uyi, 2020. – 184 b.
7. Колова С.М. Формирование социокультурной компетентности будущих специалистов. дис. ...канд. пед. наук. С. М. Колова. – Челябинск, 2002. – 190 с.
8. Елизарова, Г. В. О природе социокультурной компетенции [Текст] // Слово, предложение и текст как интерпретирующие системы. *Studia Linguistica* 8. СПб.: Тригон. 1998. С. 25–31.
9. Бердиева Х. Б. Развитие социокультурной компетентности у будущих учителей начальных классов // Педагогическое образование и наука. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 128-131.
10. Бердиева Х. Б., Бердиева Н. У. Проблемы развития социокультурной компетентности у школьников начальных классов // Евразийское Научное Объединение. – 2019. – №. 12-5. – С. 408-410.
11. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. / Begmatov E., Madvaliyev A. va boshqalar.; A.Madvaliyev tahriri ostida, 2-jild. - Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2006. – 408 b.
12. Даминов И.А. Спортивная деятельность - как фактор влияния на личность дзюдоистов / И.А. Даминов // *Academic research in educational sciences*. Volume 2, Issue 4, 2021. – pp. 1322 -1329.
13. Даминов, И. (2021). Совершенствование технико-тактической и психологической подготовки юных дзюдоистов. *Общество и инновации*, 2(11/S), 175–180.
14. Mirzaev, A. M., & Daminov, I. A. (2021). Improving The Physical Fitness Of Students Through The Conduct Of Individual Programs. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(11), 7054-7055.
15. Кошбахтиев И.А., Исмагилов Д.К., Даминов И.А. Особенности развития высшей физкультурной школы на современном этапе / И.А. Кошбахтиев, Д.К. Исмагилов, И.А. Даминов // *Молодой учёный*.- Казань, - 2015. №3 (83). – С. 874.
16. Кошбахтиев И.А., Исмагилов Д.К., Даминов И.А. Возможности реализации компенсаторных механизмов в системе учебной деятельности студентов / И.А. Кошбахтиев, Д.К. Исмагилов, И.А. Даминов // *Молодой учёный*.- Казань, - 2015. №6 (86). – С. 735.